

Transnational Island Museologies

Materials for discussion

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This publication brings together papers submitted for the 47th symposium organised by ICOFOM under the theme Transnational Island Museologies, to be held at the University of St Andrews, Scotland, 5-7 June, 2024.

The Materials for Discussion collection brings together, in an inclusive spirit, contributions selected for the symposium in the form of short articles, to prepare the ICOFOM Symposium. This publication has been made available before the symposium, in a very short time frame. In spite of the care given to the publication, some mistakes may remain.

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From Lochboisdale, South Uist, to Boisdale, Cape Breton

Fiona Mackenzie

Independent Researcher – Dingwall, Scotland

“Thig crìoch air an t-saoghal, ach mairidh gaol is ceòl”.
“The end of the world will come, but love and music will endure”.

-Traditional Scottish Gaelic proverb

The Campbells of Canna

Folklorist John Lorne Campbell’s arrival in the Outer Hebrides on 4 August 1933 (Cheape, 1996) marked the beginning of what we now know to have been an extraordinary life’s work of recovery and transmission of the Gaelic song, literary and linguistic record.

He began to explore this unusual world of the Hebrides, which was then, in his own words, “like the old Highlands of the early 19th century” (Cheape, 1996), and he continued on to become a pioneer of the modern collection and preservation of Gaelic song and story.

His background was not, however, in folklore but that of the son of the “landed gentry” of Argyll in Scotland. His family owned a large estate near Campbeltown, and he was educated in the ‘public school’ system, then he studied agricultural economics at Oxford. It was there that he developed his interest in matters of Celtic culture. His interest in the Gaelic language was inspired by hearing his father’s tenants speaking the language on the estate. He was later offered the opportunity by his father to “either learn Gaelic or learn to play the pipes” (Perman, 2013). Luckily for the world of Hebridean Island culture and language, he opted to learn the language.

After graduating in 1932, he went to live on the island of Barra in an effort to learn the language to complete fluency amongst native speakers. He met his future wife Margaret Fay Shaw of Pittsburgh, USA, in 1934. She was at that time living in North Glendale on the island of South Uist, herself collecting songs and stories and taking images of the surrounding communities. She had first come to Scotland in 1920 as a teenager to attend school in Helensburgh, sent by her family as a way of “sorting this wayward teenager”¹ out.

The Campbells married in 1935 and lived on the island of Barra for three years before buying the small farm island of Canna in 1938 (Shaw, 1993). The Campbells farmed Canna as a traditional

Hebridean, Gaelic speaking community whilst continuing their folkloring career.

¹ Born into a wealthy Pittsburgh steel making family, she was orphaned at a young age and brought up by her older sisters and aunts. She was not interested in anything at school apart from music, and so it was decided in 1920 to send her to Scotland to ‘sort her out’. This was a pivotal time in her life. She first heard Gaelic being sung by Victorian song collector Marjory Kennedy Fraser at a school recital in Helensburgh.

The private sound archive collections of John and Margaret, housed today in Canna House and owned by the National Trust for Scotland (NTS), represent a unique testament to the vigour and foresight of pre-eminent 20th century Gaelic scholarship. The Campbells left the island and its collections to the NTS as they had no children to take ownership of it.

Their recordings captured vital elements of traditional Gaelic culture, then still alive in Uist, Barra and Nova Scotia. Canna House now houses 1192 recordings (around 430 hours of material) made in the field between 1933 and 1969. Complementing the recordings is a collection of some 9000 black and white and colour images and early colour film, taken by Shaw, depicting all aspects of 20th century Hebridean life. Shaw also left her original transcriptions of the songs she heard around her in the small glen of South Uist where she lived for six years before marrying Campbell. Her diaries also provide unique and personal descriptions for us, of the people around her who entrusted their heritage to her, as well as the animals who lived alongside the humans on the croft.² Campbell also left an extensive collection of both folkloric diaries and diaries of his day-to-day work as a farm manager – Canna is a farm in its entirety. This was all conducted through multiple decades. Together these collections form a unique and priceless tapestry of a Hebridean lifestyle which has now disappeared.

The archives in Canna House have been largely inaccessible since Campbell's death in 1996 and Shaw's death in 2004. Has this affected the general awareness of the potential and content of the collections? What is the future of the archives? How is it impacted upon by being located in such a remote, rural location? It is three hours by ferry from the mainland, with extremely limited visitor accommodation and facilities on-island. To what extent is it the responsibility of the owner to create the conditions necessary to ensure open research access in accordance with the benefactor's wishes, even if the owner is not an academic institution?

After Shaw's death, the archives were curated by a lifelong friend of the Campbells, archivist Magda Sagarzazu of the Basque Country. On her retirement, I was appointed as archivist in 2015 and lived and worked on Canna, population 16, until late 2023, when family circumstances forced me to leave the island. I continue my research work on the collections (as "Canna Heritage – Dualchas Chanaigh") and am currently writing the biography of Margaret Fay Shaw.

As a Gaelic Arts practitioner myself, I am privileged to be able to use these archives in my performing work, and as part of my performance research, I research the songs collected by Campbell and Shaw.

“Diuram” – a transatlantic Gaelic lullaby

This presentation takes a closer look at just one of the songs collected by Margaret and John, both in South Uist and Nova Scotia, in 1933 and 1937 respectively (Shaw & Campbell, 1952). This song, called *Diuram*, literally travelled from Lochboisdale in the island of South Uist to Boisdale, Cape Breton. The presentation will include live sung versions of the song. How did this happen, and did it change as it crossed the ocean? What is the legacy of the song in a transatlantic context? How important is it to hear the live version of a song as opposed to a recorded version – what is the importance of learning from ‘the source’?

The Highland Clearances had a major impact on the movement of a culture from the Western Isles to North America, particularly to Nova Scotia. This greatly increased after the 1812 war between the UK and the US – the American route was effectively closed to emigrants, so they went to Canada instead. In Cape Breton, settlers from Barra concentrated around the Barra Strait in the Bras d’Or, while South Uist people went mainly to Grand Mira and the Boisdale and East Bay areas. North Uist settlers went to Catalone, Gabarus and Mira, while Harris folk went to Grand River, Framboise and St Anns.

There are many different versions of the songs recorded over the years, both by the Campbells and other collectors. However, few have travelled so far and retained their lyrical and melodic integrity as the lullaby *Diuram*. It’s interesting to see how a song can change as it crosses the years and the ocean, carrying traditions with it from one people to another yet remaining recognisably the same.

Shaw collected the song in 1933 from Peigi Nill (Mrs John Currie) in North Glendale, South Lochboisdale (Shaw, 1955). The presentation will discuss the setting of the song and its linguistic characteristics. Campbell collected *Diuram* in Antigonish County, Nova Scotia, on 20 October 1937, from the well-known singer and piper Angus ‘Ridge’ Macdonald. Comparisons between the two versions will be examined and recordings of both versions will be played. What impact if any, did the differing social environments have on the two versions of the song?

Shaw took images of the contributors in Nova Scotia who gave them their songs – does an image of the person giving the song increase our appreciation or understanding of a sound recording? These are folk songs – does this mean their social and cultural significance is lessened by being part of a folk or tribal origin?

We can learn a lot from examining the ways people preserved our heritage and culture. Separated by oceans with no social media to rely on, the songs still retain the story, the meaning and the personality of the people who made them in the first place.

The Campbells’ legacy in Canna House, including this lullaby, is testament to the respect and vision they possessed for their own adopted heritage and culture. What do we learn from their legacy today? Should we be ‘conserving’ it or ‘developing it’?

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